

Medicinal and Aromatic Plants and their role in Healthcare and Economic Development

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Abstract-Traditional medicine was the foundation of health care around the world since the early days of humanity. Medicinal plants have been known for millennia as a wealthy source of therapeutic agents for the treatment and prevention of various diseases, occupying an important place in the socio-cultural, spiritual and medical field. They are the source of primary health care for most of the world's population. Knowing and using them is a great economical source, but often unpublished. Tendencies for long-term use in the traditional health system will also increase the need for good management of their habitats. The source management systems, which should aim at the full protection of not only the nearest sources but also the farthest ones and will bring a potential market supply of medicinal plants. The open access policies, which have been implemented in the last decades, will provide more opportunities for better quality collective actions for the protection of biodiversity, sustainable management and supply of medicinal plants to the market. Thus, in the long-term vision, this sector will pass from a natural economy into a well-managed economy of its potentials. Natural medicinal substances used in folk medicine around the world will continue to contribute to health as they have done for millennia after facing some challenges. Today, this vegetation is facing various threats, such as pressure from human activities, climate change, and erosion of species. Scientific interest in medicinal plants has increased due to increased efficacy of new herbal medicines, increased interest in natural products, and growing concerns about the side effects of conventional medicine. Precisely, this article aims to review the current state of use of medical plants, resource management systems, quality concerns, and security and sales strategies for these products in global markets

Keywords: Medicinal plants, active dose, environment, management, Sustainable Development.

History of Medicinal Plants

Plant samples from the prehistoric cemetery sites are among the lines of evidence that the Paleolithic people had knowledge of the use of medicinal herbs. In ancient Sumerian, a large number of medicinal herbs have been used, such as nettles, chamomile, tatar, aloe, cannabis, beans, garlic, juniper, etc. In the fourth century (before the new era), Theophrastus, that is Aristotle's student wrote the first text "History of Plantarum." Also, Ebers Ancient Egyptian papyrus containing over 800 herbal medicines. In the first century (AD), Greek

doctor Pedanius Dioscorides documented over 1000 prescriptions for medicines using over 600 medicinal plants for their preparation. Also, in the early era, the Benedictine monasteries maintained medical knowledge in Europe through the translation, copying of classical texts and the keeping of herb gardens. Even in the Islamic Golden Age, flourishing the use of medicinal herbs flourished. Plants and technologies were transferred between the old world and America in the 15th and 16th centuries. Studies on medicinal herbs started from the sixteenth century. Manuscripts and books on herbal medicines were written mainly by Spanish missionaries. Also, traditional Chinese medicine used a wide variety of herbs, between

materials and other techniques. The pharmaceutical industry in Europe developed in the 1800s. The plant's place in medicine was radically changed in the 19th century by applying chemical analysis. In 1806, the first alkaloid was discovered, and later in 1826 Merc was the commercial extract of purified alkaloids including morphine. The discovery of plant medicines continued to be important during the 20th century and at 21, giving priority to herbal medicine. The World Health Organization estimates that about 80 percent of the world's population depends mainly on traditional medicine.

In 1991 the World Health Organization formulated a policy on traditional medicine and had since then published guidelines on how to use and care for their overdose. It has coordinated a network called "International Regulatory Cooperation for Plant Medicines" to improve the quality of medicinal products made by medicinal plants and the claims made for them. We must mention that from 1073 small molecule drugs approved in 1981-2010, more than half were of plant origin. According to the statistics of the Food and Agriculture Organization, the number of medicinal plants used in traditional medicine is different over the years. Thus, in 2002 around 50,000 medicinal plants were used, whereas in 2016 this number went to some 17,810 species, of which about 3,000 plants have been documented for their uses. By 2007, clinical trials had shown potentially beneficial activity in almost 16% of herbal medicines. A Phylogenetic Study in 2012 built a family tree up to the sex level using 20,000 species to compare the medicinal plants of the three regions, Nepal, New Zealand and South Africa. He discovered that the types traditionally used to treat the same types of disease belonged to the same plant groups in the three regions, giving a "strong phylogenetic signal." The annual value of world pharmaceuticals exports in 2012 was over 2.2 billion dollars. In many countries, there are few adjustments to traditional medicine, but the World Health Organization is coordinating a network to encourage safe and rational use. In 2015, only about 20% of countries had regular functional agencies, while 30% did not, and about half had limited regulatory capacity. Also, by 2015, most of the products made from medicinal plants were not

tested for their safety and efficacy. Over 12,000 active compounds are known to science and about 20 to 25% of medicines used in modern medicine use such chemicals derived from plants. Well-known and globally used drugs are around 120. The global number of medicinal plant species is estimated to be almost 53,000 or 10-18% of global herb plant species. (Farnsworth et al., 1985a, pp. 29-41). According to the World Health Organization, the percentage of the population over the age of 60 who will use traditional medicine as the first option in developed countries is projected to increase from 19% to 32% by 2050, which will also bring an increase in demand for traditional medicine. This trend will also accompany developing countries due to their lower prices by comparing with industrial products.

Cultivation of medicinal and aromatic herbs in Albania

Albania represents one of the European countries with a rich diversity of cultivated and wild medicinal flora (Paparasito et al., 1988), which goes to about 3250 species, of which 30 species are endemic and 180 sub-endemic species Vangjeli et al. 1995). More than 300 species have been identified as medicinal and aromatic herbs, of which 182 are the most common, most of which are exported. They are playing an important role in everyday life in traditional medicine (Vangjeli et al. 1995, Pieroni et al., 2015, Ibraliu et al., 2014). Albanian vegetation is distinguished not only for its diversity but also for the high content of essential oils. According to Demiri (1983) and Ibraliu et al. (2010), these plants are used in folk medicine practices during ancient times and continue to be used today. As part of the value chain structure, the flora of medicinal and aromatic herbs (cultivated and wild) has a major contribution to increasing the value of agricultural products in Albania. More than 95% of production is exported to international markets. Albania exports mainly raw plants and only a handful of essential oil. Cleanup lines of unprocessed products do only their prior cleaning by performing only such operations as leaf removal,

dust cleaning, stones and other external physical elements. Starting in 2011, exports grew at about 27 million dollars. In 2013, the highest level of exports was recorded, amounting to an amount (9330 tons) worth 27.3 million dollars. Also, in 2011, Albania is ranked 24th in the world for the export of medicinal and aromatic herbs. Their export has been one of the most important segments of the agricultural sector in Albania, particularly in terms of international trade (USDA 2015), which is 2008 - 2012 averaged an average of 8% in the EU and US markets. (International Trade Center: ITC 2013). It should be noted that exports of medicinal and aromatic herbs account for 18% of agricultural exports and 1.1% of total exports. (INTRACEN 2013). In addition to the EU and US markets. Other important markets are Turkey, Italy, and France. Exports have steadily increased in value over the last few years. By the end of the 2000s, the sector was largely based on wild vegetation, which has come down due to the challenges it faces today, such as genetic erosion, demographic movements of the population, soil erosion, habitat destruction, illegal constructions, etc. According to statistics, the number of employees in this sector ranges from 75,000 to 100,000 ton, while the number of small processors ranges to about 20, which process about 150-500 ton of root crops and aromatic plants (DSA 2009), respectively: Malësia e Madhe 62.3 %, Kukësi 48.6%, Kolonja 41.4% and Librazhdi 38.8%. Market analysis and sales strategies should be the top priority in the coming years. The trend of cultivating these cultures has recently been increasing, which is related to the interest of communities by seeing their cultivation not only from the medical but also economic point of view as an important source of employment for a large number of rural families especially in mountainous areas (though part-time activities). Albania is the main supplier in the USA, which imports 72% of the total of medicinal and aromatic herbs imports from Albania. Also, Albania exports to the German, Turkish, French and Italian markets. Approximately 60% of Albanians export these products to Germany, followed by France with 13% and Italy by 8%. Cultivation and collection of these plants in Albania are concentrated in Northern Albania.

Revenues from this sector in Malësia e Madhe, Kukësi and Diber reach 30% - 40% of total household income (FAO 2013), while the revenue from other activities related to forests in these areas is up to 60%. The important constraints of the limitation are lack of technology, limited financial sources and difficult access to markets. The most common medicinal and aromatic plants in Albania are: rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*), oregano (*Origanum vulgare*, mountainous tea (*Sideritis raeseri*), chamomile (*Chamomilla recutita*), clover (*Trifolium pratense*), mint (*Mentha x piperita*), lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*), basilicum (*Ocimum basilicum*), etc.

Benefits from cultivating medicinal herbs

The consumption of medicinal herbs is very dimensional and comprehensive. The analysis of the consumption of medicinal herbs is very complex because there are a large number of medicinal plants taken from different habitats and management; used by different types of users, are used in a number of preventive and curative treatments and are provided by various therapists. There are four spatial levels of analysis: international, national, local and family. Also, users' demand for medicinal plants is affected by the type and level of health threats, the threat category and the intensity level of the threat (various epidemics). However, the consumption of medicinal plants is linked to various factors and impacts, affecting the supply and demand of medicinal plants. Medicinal plants offer three main types of benefits: health benefits, financial benefits, and wider benefits to society such as employment opportunities, tax revenues, and a healthier workforce. In addition to the use in the preparation of various medicines, cooking is also used for improving the quality and increasing the value of cooking, as well as various applications such as fuel, building material, etc. The patterns of medicinal plant consumption are different in different consumers, which is related to many other factors, such as income and access to public health institutions, ethnic and gender backgrounds as well as ethnobotanical knowledge. Various

ethnobotanical studies focusing on folk medicine and medicinal plants can contribute to the field of ecological health by enhancing the care and positive relationships between the community and the environment. Ecosystem services are the benefits that people receive from ecosystems that can be: direct, indirect, material, immaterial, etc. This relationship has been more apparent in primitive communities where ecosystem health and community health coincide. A healthy environment can be defined as "sustainable" because it maintains its organization and autonomy over time "(Smith-Hall, Larsen and Pouliotof, 2000). According to the World Health Organization's assessment, medicinal plants constitute the basis of systems. In recent years, there has been an increase in interest in traditional medicine, partly driven by the interest in complementary medicine for the treatment of various diseases. The cultivation of medicinal plants, which is linked to the increase of demand in national and international markets, also increases the need for new investments and policies with the main aim of integrating health, environmental and economic policies together. Investments are also needed to develop appropriate conservation, cultivation and harvesting strategies, which will simultaneously meet the demand for low-cost and in-house medicines (Akerle et al., 1991). On the other hand, these investments should also serve to regenerate species for future yields. It should be noted that the consequences of the loss of plant diversity around the world are alarming because a considerable number of them are at risk limits mainly from habitat destruction and neglect during harvest which has led to their non-production. This problem is related to the fact that there is little or no legislation limiting the uncritical exploitation of their habitats, which is the result of increased market demand. Thus, according to a World Bank study, any strategy for the cultivation of medicinal plants should consider: promoting the use of medicinal herbs in health care programs, product standardization policies, incentives to encourage local community participation in collection and the implementation of sustainable development policies for resource management. In addition, their cultivation provides many opportunities, such as

employment opportunities in trade and the industry of medicinal plants as processors or retailers and health care providers, and increased government revenues from taxes related to medical plants such as licenses for harvesting, transportation permits, customs duties and value-added tax.

Negative effects of plant products

Plants contain many chemical compounds for biological functions, including protection against insects, fungi, mammals, etc. These chemicals act in the human body in the same way as pharmaceuticals. Herbal medicines can be beneficial but have harmful side effects, even deaths, just as conventional medicines. There are many unknown and undetected medicinal plants on their benefits and safety, which need to be scientifically explored. These plants are also used in modern medicine because they are used as sources of direct therapeutic agents. It should be noted that there is no reason to suppose that because the product comes from nature must be safe, for example, the existence of powerful natural toxins such as atropine and nicotine shows that this is untrue. Moreover, the high standards applied to conventional medicines are not always applied to plant medicines and doses may vary greatly depending on growing conditions and plant age (older plants may be much more toxic than new plants). From the surveys made, the content of the active substance is different in different plant organs, respectively: the roots contain 44.3%, leaves 23.6% and fruits 11.8%. For many years, people have had free access to medical services. Price range depends on the type of disease, season and availability of medicinal herbs. Since plants may contain different substances, plant extracts may have complex effects on the human body. In developed countries, plant raw materials and extracts are of little importance as drugs, but there is a steady growth in their use, especially in Europe. In the last decade, a tremendous effort has been set to lead to the isolation of many bioactive drugs from plants because synthetic products are considered unsafe, while plant products seem to symbolize safety. Although plant medications seem relatively safe, there are many dilemmas in their use

due to limited human research related to unwanted effects and their interactions. Official statistics on trade and consumption of medicinal plants are scarce and not very informative because medicinal plant products are often part of the informal economy. Therefore they are not part of the government-monitored economy, taxation or inclusion in national statistical evaluations such as national product gross. Increased attention to the consumption of medicinal plants can contribute to the development of cooperation across natural resources and health sectors, resulting in more comprehensive and efficient health policies. The importance of medicinal plants in health care is becoming increasingly popular in the health sector. Achieving the Millennium Development Goals to increase healthcare requires the implementation of long-term and contemporary management strategies of these resources and the integration of plant medicines into national health legislation.

Cultivation of medicinal herbs and challenges

Cultivation of medicinal herbs requires intensive management, which cannot be seen separately from the general forest management. Public cultivation policies should aim to safeguard economic, social and environmental standards. This can be accomplished if there is a will to cultivate and protect them because they often face general and specific threats. General threats include climate change and habitat loss, while specific threats relate to the excessive collection to meet growing demand for medicines, mainly wild populations. On the other hand, we must emphasize that it is in the economic interest of each country that governmental farming policies focus on sustainable economic development. Applying incorrect cultivation and collection practices is extremely harmful to some species that have slower growth and smaller renewable opportunities. The destruction of habitat as the main cause of depletion of natural resources results from the expansion of population and human activities. Conservation should also be seen as the wise use of natural resources, a view that implies the need to select, for each habitat and social context, the use of resources in accordance with the degree of conservation necessary to ensure their renewal. In the long-term

vision, this sector has to move from a natural economy to a well-managed economy of its potentials. The World Health Organization recommends the use of rotation to minimize problems with pests and diseases of these herbs. The different communities and countries would face with a lot of challenges, such as: implementing new technologies of cultivation, integration, security, guarantee, training of growers, product marketing, and information problems. There is currently a little effort in Albania to increase the production of medicinal plants through good resource management. It should be noted that in Albania, even though it has large resources, the collected product results in limited quantities. This reduced supply is linked to a number of challenges, such as population migration, habitats (traceability), harvesting manner or harvesting times, storage and quality standards. Failure to implement sustainable development practices will lead to the constant erosion of species. Such challenges should be part of the practices, plans, and programs of development, which will also bring a continuous public-private cooperation, in order to improve the competitiveness and sustainability of the sector. Development strategies should focus on selling these products not only to local markets but also to national and international markets. Sustainable management of medicinal plant species is important, not only because of their value as a potential source of new drugs but also because of the support in medicinal plants for primary health care. However, there is a paradox in the current approach to the discovery of drugs derived from natural resources. On the one hand, there are many successful current medicines that have leaked from natural materials, especially plants, but we also have medicines manufactured by the pharmaceutical industries. (Olayiwola Akerele pp. 11-16). Global policies and multilateral international conventions, such as the "Convention on Biological Diversity" and the "Agreement on Trade Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights," affect national policies, legislation, and budgets with impacts on the supply and demand of medicinal plants. Policies and budgets should focus on resource management, rehabilitation of degraded

areas, and the introduction of new cultivation technologies. Problems of ownership and organization of the territory in many developing countries have also exacerbated the production and the marketing of medicinal plants as a result of the reduction of the surface and quality of forest areas, which has led to a reduction in their resource base. Changes in production systems can directly affect lifestyle strategies and the type and level of health threats encountered in the country. Policies and budgets also affect the demand for medicinal plants by defining national health policies and local access to healthcare options through public funding of hospitals of relevant communities.

Conclusion:

As we see the trend of medicinal herbs has experienced constant shaking due to damaged resources and reduced workforce as a result of the migration of residents of the respective areas. In addition, this sector faces a number of challenges that relate mainly to the practices of cultivating, storing and securing sales markets. Addressing these issues should be a priority for government development policies and for ongoing co-operation of the public-private sector in order to improve the competitiveness and sustainability of the sector. Studies should focus on a comprehensive approach that is needed to illustrate and understand the multiple and complex factors affecting the consumption of them. Special attention should be paid to technology-related issues such as soil, seed, collection, storage, standardization, packaging, transportation, and sales markets. The main approach should focus on combining efforts from one side of the plant's trading companies and on the other end to the companies of recent users and consumers.

Although the problem of wild harvesting is of international interest, perhaps the developed world must first try to reduce the demand for such material. Collective consumer pressure is a powerful tool to bring about changes in trading practices. As such, consumers should become aware of problems with the trade of medicinal herbs and are encouraged to buy only products produced from cultured plants or collected on a sustainable basis. A very good option is to use an international logo

similar to those used for recycled commodities or organically cultivated foods. Global policy implementation, international multilateral conventions and budget drafting policies, which should focus on resource management, rehabilitation of degraded areas and the introduction of new cultivation technologies play an important role.

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